

Various researchers opinion about lime fixation point on Non-expansive and expansive soil-an over view

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ABSTRACT

Soil in general grouped into two types, one is non-expansive soil and another one is expansive soil. Red earth is treated as pure non – expansive soil where as Black cotton soil is treated as pure Expansive soil, However, Shedi soil (lateritic soil) is treated as intermediate of these two types of soil. To enhance the strength of any soil, stabilization of soil is required. One of the good old best stabilization method is chemical stabilization technique. In this review paper an attempt has been made to study the optimization techniques adopted by various researchers in lime fixation point on both non-expansive soil and expansive soil. From the review of the literature it has been found that for non-expansive soil- lime fixation is in the range of 2 to 3% (by weight of soil) where as in expansive soil- lime fixation is in the range of 4 to 6% (by weight of soil). However for both non-expansive soil and expansive soil addition of lime reduces the maximum dry density and marginally increases the optimum moisture content of the matrix.

Key words: Lime fixation point, non-expansive soil and expansive soil

Introduction

Indian terrain is formed by various types of soil depositions. Some of the soil formations exhibit problems for design and construction of civil engineering structures. Some of the problematic soils are as follows: Black cotton soils, occurring in Maharashtra, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, Karnataka, parts of Andhra Pradesh and Tamil Nadu. These are expansive in nature. On account of high swelling and shrinkage potential these are difficult soils to deal with civil engineering designs. Marine soils, occurring in a narrow belt all along the coast, especially in the Rann of Kutch. These are very soft and sometimes contain organic matter, possess low strength and high compressibility. Desert soils, occurring in Rajasthan. These are deposited by wind and are uniformly graded. Alluvial soils, occurring in the Indo-Gangetic plain, north of the Vindhya ranges. Lateritic soils, occurring in Kerala, South Maharashtra, Karnataka, Orissa and West Bengal.

Some of the beds in the coastal area do not show the behaviour of clay or silt, but when it comes in contact with water it flows like water, which will cause lot of settlement and this bed soil is termed as shedi soil. The construction of foundation for structure, construction of embankment, construction of road on shedi soil poses a challenge to civil engineers. Chemical stabilization is one of the oldest methods of stabilization for problematic soil.(Darshan (2014) M.Tech thesis)

Black cotton soil is major problematic soil of some tropical countries particularly in Africa and India. They are poor materials by temperate zone standards and difficult to use for highway and air field construction, since they are frequently far reaching because of the presence of vast rates of expansive clay minerals, called as Montmorillonite. These soils swell when in contact with water and shrink on drying. The soils deposits are generally broad making it difficult to stay away from or by pass during construction of engineering projects. Many roads and establishments of light structures have subjected to reduction in strength upon wetting and developing shrinkage cracks on drying due to volume change behaviour.

Bulk quantity of soil is utilized as a part of the construction of roads / highways, as a sub grade material or as an embankment material. Any way adequate amount of soil of required quality isn't accessible effortlessly. For that reason large amount of trees are being cut which cause deforestation, soil disintegration and loss of fertile soil which hampers in the agricultural efficiency. Additionally, cost of extracting good quality material is expanding. These industrial wastes which are utilized as a substitute for regular soil in the construction not just to take care of the issues related to disposal and ecological contamination yet in addition help to preserve the natural soil. The challenge for the present and future of road construction is the proper usage of waste or industrial by-products as constructing materials. This will give various advantages to the constructing industry and additionally to the nation in general by conservation of natural resources, by decrease of volume of waste to landfills, by bringing down the cost of construction materials, reducing down waste disposal costs, and the last but not the least by promoting a "clean and green" image. (Lakshmesh (2018) M.Tech thesis)

2. Review of Literature from few researchers

In order to optimize the lime fixation point in general few available published papers and theses were studied they are as follows

Prakash *et.al* (1989) says that, lime affects the index property and engineering property of expansive soil. They concluded that montmorillonitic soil stabilized with lime decreases the maximum dry density as the specific gravity of lime is generally lower than the specific gravity of tested soil and increases the optimum moisture content due to pozzolanic reaction between soil particles and lime. Jacques Locas *et.al* (1990) says that, lime affects the strength behaviour of sensitive clay. They concluded that addition of quick lime with sensitive clay increases the strength even at water content more than liquid limit. The optimum variation was observed at 0.5% quick lime (by weight of soil) in sensitive clay. (Dallas *et.al* (1997)(extracted from Darshan M.Tech thesis)) says that, lime stabilizes the clayey soil and produces long term strength and reduces the plasticity of soil. They concluded that, addition of lime increases bearing capacity of clayey soil and reduce the swell-shrinkage behaviour. The optimum variation was observed at optimum lime content. Peter *et.al* ((1997))(extracted from Darshan M.Tech thesis)) says that, lime affects the strength characteristics of soft clayey soil. They concluded that, the addition of lime improves the shear strength and workability of the soil. The optimum variation was observed for 2.5% - 3.5% of lime content (by weight of soil) at the end of 28 days. Kate *et.al* (2009) says that, addition of lime affects the swelling behaviour of expansive soil. They concluded that addition hydrated lime $[Ca(OH)_2]$ to expansive soil decreases swelling

pressure and improve strength. The optimum variation was observed at 4% lime content (by weight of soil) in soil. Ramesh *et.al* (2010) says that, addition of lime-coir fiber affects the compaction and strength behaviour black cotton soil. They concluded that expansive soil stabilized with lime-coir fiber decreases the dry density and compressive strength of soil. The optimum variation in black cotton soil was observed at 4% lime (by weight of soil) and 1% (by weight of soil) fiber content with aspect ratio 20. Al-Kiki *et.al* (2011) says that, with the increase in lime content, the maximum dry unit weight decreases, this reduction is due to the immediate reaction between lime and soil, and optimum moisture content increases due to increase fine materials also due to the hydration of lime. Ramakrishne gowda *et al* (2011) says that, plasticity index of the shedi soil decreases and optimum moisture content increases with increasing concentration of alkalie content in the fluid and they concluded that swell pressure and compressibility of soil decreases essentially due to decrease in the cohesion of the soil particles. Twinkle *et.al* (2011) They concluded that with addition of lime and polypropylene fiber to expansive soil, the liquid limit decrease with increase in plastic limit, maximum dry density decreases with increase in optimum moisture content, the swelling potential decreases with increase in compressive strength. The optimum variation was observed for 4% lime and 0.8% fiber in soil. Sreedhar *et.al* (2011) conducted pond ash stabilized with lime by adding lime with level of 2,5,10,20% (by weight of soil) and the California bearing ratio samples were prepared by using heavy compaction test for a soaking periods of 4 days,7 days and 28 days, they found that the soaking period increase California bearing ratio value is also increases with increasing in percentage of lime , they found that stabilization of pond ash with lime is not only control the fly by air nature, but also improves the California bearing ratio value significantly, hence it can be used as effective overlay or soft sub grade pavement. Manoj Krishna *et.al* (2012) says that, addition of lime affects the strength behaviour of black cotton soil. They concluded that expansive soil stabilized with lime increases the bearing capacity of soil. The optimum variation was observed at 3% lime content (by weight of soil) in soil. Nadgouda *et.al* (2012) says that, addition of lime affects the engineering behaviour of black cotton soil. They concluded that expansive soil stabilized with lime increases the dry density and reduces the liquid limit of soil. The optimum variation was observed at 3.5% - 4.5% lime content (by weight of soil) in soil. Ramesh *et.al* (2012) says that, addition of lime affects engineering properties of the red earth soil. They concluded that non expansive soil stabilized with lime increases the unconfined compressive strength of soil. The optimum variation was observed at 3% lime content (by weight of soil) in soil. Raju *et.al* (2012) they studied geotechnical behaviour of pond ash mixed with marble dust, they found that as the pore water pressure increases, deviator stress is also increases and axial strain is also increases, which indicate more and more ductile behaviour in the matrix. Pandey *et.al* (2013) says that, the value of optimum moisture content increases and maximum dry density decreases initially in 25% flyash and 5% lime content.. Rajendra (2013) the conducted the grain size distribution analysis by mixing black cotton soil with varies percentage of fly ash (10 to 100%) with an incremental of 10% fly ash (by weight of the soil), with a percentage of fly ash increase, percentage of gravel fraction decreases and finer sand fraction increase, where as silty and clayey remains unaltered and also found that addition of lime to fly ash. Free swell index decreases which indicate the control in the behaviour of swelling. Due to important in plastic characteristics that is black cotton soil with fly ash, plasticity index

decreases and the classification of soil changes from clay of higher to silt of higher due to the improvements in the plastic characteristics black cotton soil for base coarse as a stabilizing materials. Ashish Mehta et.al (2013) they found that black cotton soil treated with 10 to 80% of fly ash with an increment of 10% (by weight of soil). The soaked California bearing ratio value of soil treated with fly ash is lower than the soil alone where as unsoaked California bearing ratio value is higher than the soil alone. From the unsoaked California bearing ratio test soil stabilized with 20% pond ash is found to be optimum, this is because low unit weight of fly ash makes well suited for placement or soft of low bearing capacity. Harshita Bairagi et.al (2014) says that, black cotton soil with 5% lime and jute fiber from 0% to 5%(by dry weight of soil) increases shrinkage limit and also they concluded that California bearing ratio and Unconfined compressive strength values increases and swelling behaviour of black cotton soil decreases. Karthik et.al (2014) they found that, soil treated with varying percentage of pond ash; there will be a marginal variation of Maximum dry density and improvements of California bearing ratio value. Girish and Sushma (2015) conducted “Performance analysis of pond ash as a partial replacement to black cotton soil for pavement sub grade construction”, they are added 10 to 25% of pond ash (by weight of the soil) to the black cotton soil and they found that increases of percentage pond ash to black cotton Soil, maximum dry density increases up to 15% of pond ash, optimum moisture content decreases when compared with soil alone, they are also conducted California bearing ratio value for black cotton soil with varying percentage of pond ash corresponding to optimum moisture content is found that 20% pond ash in black cotton soil improves the California bearing value by 1.53% when compared to the other combination. Surendra and Hussain (2015) they are treated the soil by adding fly ash and lime and found that, liquid limit decreases as the percentage of fly ash increases and they found that drastic reduction in the value of liquid limit. In immediate testing, soil treated with lime is due to reduction in specific surface area, consequently diffused in double layer thickness, possible accounts for the lower liquid limit treated soil during initial stage, they also says that, liquid limit decreases with increasing in percentage of lime concentration in the soil , this is because of decreases in the diffused double layer, it leads to the increasing in shearing resistance, soil fabric varies with change in the exchangeable ion depending on the shape and size of holes present in the matrix. Addition of lime in soil increases the California bearing ratio value, the reason for increases California bearing ratio value with increasing in lime or ash is related to these voids which are not filled with cementing product, the bonding of the clay particle is due to pozzolanic reaction is limited by increasing fly ash, lime and also due to presence of water particles. Bibha and Duggal (2015) they says that, thermal power plant after burning the coal 20 to 30% of fly ash which are settled at the bottom may be disposed using in the form of slurry which is called as pond ash. They also concluded that the addition of fly ash substantially decreases in the value of maximum dry density and increase in corresponding optimum moisture content value both for clayey and silty soil. Hima Latheef et.al (2016) they conducted strength test by adding soil with varying percentage of pond ash (0 to 80% with an increment of 20%), they found that soil treated with 60% pond ash(by weight of the soil) strength improved by 15%, beyond that strength decreases as compared with soil alone. To further enhancement of strength, optimum black cotton soil with pond ash 1% coir fibre is added, addition of 1% coir fiber further increases the strength carrying capacity and similar trend were observed in California

bearing ratio value and they also found that pond ash treated soil reinforced with coir fiber decreases the thickness of the pavement on compared with soil alone Sambre and Naik (2016) they are conducted stabilization of soil experiment by adding soil with varying percentage of pond ash as one combination (10 to 40% by increment of 10% pond ash) in the soil and 5% fly ash stabilized soil treated with varying percentage of lime concentration. As the admixture in the soil increases, they found that there is an increase in specific gravity value, liquid limit and plastic limit value, further they also found that as the admixture in the soil increase around 15% improvements in the unconfined compression strength of the soil, they conclude that soil treated with pond ash and fly ash with presence of admixture (lime) improves the behaviour of soil and also eco-friendly approach can be developed for optimal disposal of ash as a stabilizing material in the soil. Sharmila and Sukumar (2016) they found that in a clay soil stabilized with 20% pond ash, 3% lime, 5% mosaic dust, the California bearing ratio value increased by 21% by compared to soil alone and also due to presence of lime, the matrix controls the swelling potential of clay, thus concluded that improvements in strength and reduction in swelling potential because of effective cementations particle due to presence of lime. Ankit soni et.al (2017) conducted a shear strength test for sand stabilized with varying percentage of pond ash by preparing soil to their optimum moisture content-Maximum dry density. They concluded from that, the addition of pond ash up to 15% (by weight of the soil) to sand cohesion increases and marginal improvement in angle of internal friction, there after shear strength parameter decreases. They further enhance shear strength parameter by adding 8% lime (by weight of the soil). Krithiga et.al (2017) they concluded that soil stabilizing by using lime and fly ash is very effective process of strengthening of soil and they also found that, the above stabilized mixture improves the bearing capacity of soil and they recommended in any type of foundation on such soil. Deepak and Arvind (2017) conducted the surface morphological characteristics of soil and pond ash specimen after 7gdays of curing; they found that from scanning electronic microscopy, formation of calcium silicate hydrate (C-S-H) gel in the analysis, they also found that the presence of some elongated crystallizing structure and these are responsible for pozzolanic activity taking place in the soil and pond ash, they also found that increases in the combined dosage of rice husk ash and pond ash, increases in maximum dry density and enhance the optimum moisture content, they said that relatively lower the specific gravity value of pond ash might be cause reduction in maximum dry density value and they also found that soil stabilized with cementitious material further decreases the maximum dry density value, the fall in the density is due to the quick reaction of cement with the soil, which alters the base exchange aggregation and flocculation thereby resulting of increases in void ratio of the mixture, thus subsequently leads to decreases in density of the overall mixtures. Pond ash replacing clay particle because of which overall weight of the mixture decreases and becomes a light weight structure, such type of light weight mixture preferable in light weight embankment wall construction, they also conducted California bearing ratio test for clay stabilized with pond ash, they found that the addition of pond ash to clay, California bearing ratio increases because clay as a mainly cohesion component against the deformation, due to the addition of pond ash frictional component also contributed resistance against deformation and hence load carrying capacity of clay and pond ash matrix increases. The optimal increase has been observed with 40% pond ash in black cotton soil. In general for

clay soil with addition of optimum cement, they found there will be increases in California bearing ratio value around 4%. However with a addition of pond ash to lime treated clay soil California bearing ratio value increased by 6 folds more than the previous case, they analysis that soaked California bearing ratio of clay is less than the unsoaked California bearing ratio value of clay soil, this is because during the soaked condition surface tension forces which were offering additional resistance to penetration against the loading are destroyed but when the clay soil stabilized with pond ash or cement under soaked condition, the California bearing ratio value will also increases because pond ash as well as cement initiate the pozzolanic reaction between clay and pozzolanic material which leads to formation of additional cementations material that bound further together which leads to enhancement of the strength in the soil. Pravin and Damgir (2017) they found that with 10% fly ash and 4% lime increases the California bearing ratio value by 2 folds compared with lower concentration of fly ash.

Conclusions

Based on the detail literature review, followed by the outcome of the already published papers following conclusions were drawn

1. Addition of lime to Non-expansive or expansive soil maximum dry density decreases and marginally increase in optimum moisture content
2. Non-expansive soil the lime fixation point in the range of 2 to 3% in general
3. Expansive soil the lime fixation point in the range of 4 to 6 % in general

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NOTATIONS

BCS=Black Cotton Soil

MDD=Maximum Dry Density

RE=Red Earth Soil

SS=Shedi Soil

OMC=Optimum Moisture Content

%=Percentage